

A STUDY ON BUYING BEHAVIOR OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS AMONG UNDERGRADUATE LEVEL FEMALE STUDENTS WITH REFERENCE TO BELTHANGADY TALUK OF DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT.

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ABSTRACT

From the ancient literature to present all poets, writers have been symbolizing beauty to women. Beauty has been matter of concern and is the main subject to market any product for the marketer, in any advertisements, whether related or not marketers cast women as a symbol of beauty Majority of the women are beauty conscious when comparing to men they have got highly sensitive and soft skin, all females tend to purchase and use cosmetics either to safeguard their sensitive skin or to look beautiful. When we compare cities with rural areas cities are much smarter with all infrastructure facilities but rural areas are lagging behind so the people are. Buying behavior changes from one person to another because of difference in personal stimuli, perception and other factors. In cities people can get goods of their choice with ease but this is not so in the case of rural areas especially when they are lacking in transportation facility and network connectivity. Majority of the rural females are daily wage workers who work in either in the paddy fields or Areca estates. This paper is an outcome of an attempt made to know about the buying behavior of the undergraduate level rural female students of belthangady taluk while purchasing the cosmetic products, paper also highlights opportunities for the marketers to serve better and scope for entrepreneurship.

Key words: - Rural female students, opportunities for the marketers, entrepreneurship

INTRODUCTION

From the ancient literature to present all poets, writers have been symbolizing women to beauty. Beauty has been a matter of concern and is the main subject for to the market any product to the marketers in any advertisements whether related or not marketers cast women as a symbol of beauty.

Majority of the women are beauty conscious. When comparing to men they have got highly sensitive and soft skin, all females tend to purchase and use cosmetics either to safeguard their sensitive skin or to look beautiful. When we compare cities with rural areas cities are much smarter with all infrastructure but rural areas are lagging behind so the people are. The cost of living in rural area is much less than the cities and rural people will have a different consumption pattern, priorities because of connectivity and other socio economic causes.

Every individual is having urge or desire or stimuli, when a certain offering matches with his desire or urge or stimuli it creates demand. And certain set of activities shown by him in satisfying his stimuli or urge collectively called as buying behavior.”¹ behavior is the total response which man makes to the situations in life with which either is confronted”.

A buying behavior is the behavior shown by the consumer or customer while prioritizing the product or shop. There are two types of buying behavior.

1. Buying behavior shown on purchasing the particular product with reference to other products.
 2. Buying behavior shown in preferring one particular shop with reference to other shops.
- Both above types of buying behaviors are influenced by various factors such as
- a) Price
 - b) Product packaging and way of display in shops
 - c) Impact of salesmen
 - d) Offers and discounts
 - e) Quality of the product and good will of the shops
 - f) Buyers personal beliefs
 - g) Distance of shops
 - h) Availability of products etc.,

Because of easy accessibility to social media, growing peer group circle through whats app and other “friendly apps” the youth of rural areas have been modernizing themselves. Nowadays they quickly adapt to modern trends. This paper is an outcome of an attempt made to know about the buying behavior depicted in purchasing cosmetics by undergraduate level students who falling from rural areas of belthangady taluk of Dakshina kannada district.

OBJECTIVES:

- To know about the buying behavior of female undergraduate students with respect of cosmetic products.
- To know about consumption pattern
- To know about brand preference
- To know about satisfaction level
- To know about easy availability of cosmetic products in rural areas

STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

Majority of the respondents are from the rural and from economically weaker sections, where the male and female senior members of the families are involved as coolie either in paddy fields or in areca estates. Since they are from rural area from economically weaker sections authors have

made an attempt to know about their buying behavior with respect of cosmetics and expenditure pattern on them.

METHODOLOGY

Based on the requirements of the study, data is collected from secondary sources such as published books, online PDF files reports of various authors and at the same time by structured questionnaire method. 63 samples were collected through Google form with structured set of questions. Convenient method of non-random sampling is followed to meet the objectives of the study in belthangady region.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

MRS. J. VIDHYA JAWAHAR AND DR. K. TAMZHJYOTHI (2013) held in their study “consumer attitude towards cosmetic products” that middle aged people have positive attitude towards cosmetic products compared to young aged people to keep themselves young or to give young appearance. And family income won’t effect upon the attitudes towards beauty cosmetic products.

DR. M.SHAJAHANAN AND DR. S. MOHAMMED SAFI (2019) in their study on consumer behavior with respect of cosmetic products in tiruchirappalli district held that consumers will buy products by observing products through TV and they buy from fancy stores for every 15 days.

SCHIFMAN, KANUK (2009) consumers who had no experience with a product will trust well known brand name. Consumers think that well known brands are better and are worth buying for implied assurance of quality dependability, performance and service.

KOTLER (2004) because of difference in human psychology, demographical difference and age and sex every consumer exhibits different approaches while buying and in some situations consumer’s selection and choice is influenced by the family.

GEOGRAPHIC AND DEMOGRAPHIC VIEW OF BELTHANGADY TALUK²

Belthangady taluk is mostly covered by forests and hills of Western Ghats. This taluk has an average elevation of 685 meters (2247 feet) it covers an area of 1375 square kilometers.

As per 2001 census, belthangady taluk had a population of 2, 46,494 with 1, 21,288 males (49.2%) and 1,25,206 females (50.8%) the taluk is covered with 02.9% urban area and 97.1% in rural area.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

PART – A Table.1: profile of the respondents

Particulars	No. of respondents		Percentage
Total number of respondents	63		100
Graduation stream	B.A	20	31.74
	B.COM	25	40.00
	B.C.A	13	20.63
	BNSY	03	04.76
	BPED	02	03.17
	Total	63	

Source: survey

The PART –A consist of basic information of the respondents. Data is collected from total 63 female respondents who are studying in undergraduate colleges of Belthangady taluk. It is also evident that majority of the respondents are from traditional courses.

PART –B Table 1: frequency of purchasing cosmetic products

Frequency	No. of respondents	Percentage
Rarely	34	53.96
Frequently	14	22.22
Very rarely	15	23.81
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above data it is clear that more than 50% of the respondents are purchasing the product rarely and very rarely(total together 77.67%). As respondents are young and they falling from rural background further their economic condition also have influence over purchase frequency.

Table 2: type of cosmetic product used

Product	No. of respondents	Percentage
Powder+ eyeliner+ lipstick	38	60.31
Only eyeliner	04	6.34
Only lipstick	03	4.76

Only powder	11	17.47
Any other	07	11.11
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above table it is clear that respondents prefer to buy combo packs. 60.31% of the respondents purchase three products together. Marketers will have a better market if they market in combos. It is evident that there is less demand for single product.

Table 3: purpose of using cosmetics

Purpose	No. of respondents	Percentage
Facial care	28	44.44
Young looks	08	12.69
Improving self image	22	34.92
To look attractive to others	05	7.94
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

Majority of the respondents use cosmetics for facial care (44.44%), as they are young they won't use to look young only minute percentage use cosmetics to look young. And 34.92% of the respondents use to improve self image and 7.94% uses to look attractive to others. There is much scope for facial care products such as face washes etc.,

Table 4: brand preference of the respondents

Brand	No. of respondents	Percentage
Lakme	23	36.50
ponds	13	20.63
Dazzler	18	28.57
Any other	09	14.29
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

Majority of the respondents prefer lakme products over other products and 28.57% of people prefer dazzler product. And 20.63% of people use ponds .This is because these are the very popular brands in the locality because of their quality.

Table 5: factor influencing selection of cosmetic brand

Factors	No. of respondents	Percentage
Peer group influence	04	6.34
Quality	47	74.60
Advertisements	05	7.94
Ingredients	07	11.11
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above table it is clear that more than 50% (74.60%) of the respondents seek quality while selecting the cosmetic brand, there is less influence of peer groups and advertisements.

Table 6: factor influencing selection of product

Factors	No. of respondents	Percentage
Features and quality	37	58.73
Brand	12	19.05
Price	10	15.87
Discounts	04	6.35
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above table it is clear that more than 50% of the respondents seek quality in products over other characteristics such as brand price and discounts.

Table 7: purchase of cosmetics from

Preference	No. of respondents	Percentage
General stores	32	50.79
Medical shops	26	41.27
Fancy shops	01	1.59
Online shopping	04	6.35
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

As the respondents are falling from rural background they don't have Access to sophisticated specialized shops and majority of the respondents purchase cosmetics from local general stores (50.79%) and medical shops (41.27%). And there is very less number for fancy shops and online shopping.

Table 8: influence of sales men or beautician over purchase

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	23	36.50
No	35	55.55
May be	05	7.94
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

It is observed that along with quality consideration near about 36% of respondents also influenced by salesmen and beautician over their purchase and 55% of respondents responded negatively. And 7% of respondents are not in the position to decide whether they are influenced or not.

Table 9: patronizing beauty parlor

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	21	33.33
No	42	66.66
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the above data it is clear that majority of the respondents are not frequent to beautify parlors this so because there is difficulty in accessing parlors. Parlors are situated in urban areas of rural areas so there is no easy access. People have to come to urban areas for the beauty parlors and there are no timely transportation facilities and this fact creates opportunities for self employment in this field.

Table 10: Easy Availability of Cosmetics

Response	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	33	52.38
No	30	47.61
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

As the respondents are residing in rural areas the availability of cosmetic products is less. The local shop keepers more concentrate on daily and essential needs of the customers and they keep products accordingly, near about 47.61% of the respondents responded negatively.

Table 11: Monthly expenditure on cosmetics

Amount	No. of respondents	Percentage
100 -200	35	55.55
500-1000	13	20.63
1000 and above	05	07.94
Depends on the product	10	15.87
TOTAL	63	100

Source: survey

From the table above it is clear that near about 55.55% of respondents spend below 200 Rs on cosmetics and there are less number of respondents who like to spend high priced products.

FINDINGS

- ❖ From the study we found out that majority of the female students rarely purchase cosmetics. May be because of non availability products or may be because of economic background the study has limitation in these areas.
- ❖ It was found that majority of the respondents are having concern towards facial skin and about to improve self image marketer can consider these factors to market better.
- ❖ It was found that respondents prefer only popular products and they consider quality while purchasing product and in selection of brand.

- ❖ It is observed that respondents have purchased from general stores and medical shops than fancy and online shopping.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents are not frequent to beauty parlors may be because of less number of parlors or improper transport services in rural areas this study has limitation in these aspects.
- ❖ There is improper supply of cosmetics and are not easily available in the rural areas and the majority of the respondents used to spend below 200 Rs.

CONCLUSION:

Human behavior is not programmed like any computer, human beings are of all senses and they show different behavior at different situations. Social media, technological growth made everybody smart even today's kid knows better than older generation with respect of technology. But growth in technology, social Medias made less impact on the buying behavior of cosmetics in rural areas. Only qualitative products and those products which are available easily in the locality at low price are preferred, further there are ample opportunities for the female individuals for the self employment in the rural areas as they can start a business as a beautician.

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²<https://ipfs.io/ipfs/.../wiki/Belthangady.html>